

THE ROLE OF WORLD VIEW IN THE EDUCATION OF A PERFECT GENERATION

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Since the beginning of human society, raising a perfect generation has been an urgent task. Raising a mature generation is multifaceted. It should be a priority task to form a worldview, especially among young people. The worldview is introduced into the mind of a person from the outside, and it takes place from his heart by means of certain customs, rituals, ceremonies. In this sense, it has a social classification. Feeling the world and understanding the world has an individual character. On the basis of these worldviews, a way of thinking is formed, and a person accordingly determines the long-term direction of behavior and activity. Since the Constitution of Uzbekistan envisages the creation of a secular state, a scientific and philosophical outlook is formed during the educational process in kindergartens, schools, universities and other institutions.

The worldview of young people should be in a scientific and philosophical direction, and the religious worldview should develop within the interests of building a secular state in the republic. Because with the formation of a scientific-philosophical worldview, a unique obstacle appears in the way of religious extremism. Our current education system provides too much scientific information to young people. But in this process, the formation of a scientific and philosophical worldview, and the education of people of faith on this basis, should not be

overlooked. To become a qualified specialist, it is necessary to have almost all the information and knowledge related to a particular field.

Spiritual and moral purification, faith, honesty, piety, honor, kindness and similar real human qualities do not come by themselves. Education is the basis of everything.

A student means, first of all, a seeker of knowledge. Therefore, the student's devotion to the country, selflessness, and patriotism are manifested in the desire for knowledge, the search for knowledge, the acquisition of knowledge, and the acquisition of knowledge. If the proverb "Don't put off today's work for tomorrow" is used in relation to science: "What if I complete this task tomorrow", "What if I read the book later", "I will clean my room another day, the sky will not fall to the ground", "I will learn a foreign language later, God's day is many"... this is the philosophy of a lazy person, self-deception.

If we look at history, the main indicator of perfection in any society is manifested in the attitude of a person to goodness, social happiness, humanistic ideas and practical activities based on them, that is, the criterion of perfection, which has a positive effect on the general development of society and human civilization, makes the society happy through the perfection of the individual. has been to do. Perfection in a person is, first of all, in his understanding of the freedom of thought, thinking and practical activity. In this sense, the call of the great Greek philosopher Socrates: "Know thyself" is also a call to understand one's lineage, the meaning of life, one's responsibility and obligation to future generations.

Social, political, economic, spiritual-organizational tasks for raising a perfect person in Uzbekistan are defined as the most important and priority direction of state policy because freedom and independence create the necessary conditions for the realization of the ideal of a perfect person.

Our head of state: "In the formation of a free person, we must educate free, well-rounded people who recognize their rights, rely on their own strength and capabilities, approach the events around them with an independent attitude, and at the

same time, see their personal interests in harmony with the interests of the country and the people." , they showed that this lesson imposes a high responsibility on every citizen and the mature generation.

We must not forget that raising a perfect person is a complex process. Unfortunately, we often have a one-sided attitude towards this responsible work. According to the teachings left by the wise, it is necessary to look not at the goal, but at the path leading to the goal. Most of us have decided to work based on the old adage that education is for education. There is an unsophisticated one who seeks to educate. But do the superficial lectures and long lectures we are reading have the desired effect? Does the continuous educational influence penetrate into the hearts of young people, or does inner-spiritual resistance arise, causing trainers to fall into an unfavorable situation? If we remember the words of President Islam Karimov, which are repeated many times on television: "...let's listen to the spiritual world of young people, let's try to understand their inner-spiritual world", it is not a conclusion that we have been careless and indifferent towards young people, that we have failed to educate them, but that we have forced them to educate them. The conclusion is that we thought little about understanding them, listening to their hearts. Due to our indifference and, at the same time, our excessive strictness, negative vices are forming in the nature of some young people: selfishness, hypocrisy, suspicion. The position of parents, teachers, and social institutions in the matter of education is incomparable. But we need to understand one thing: it is not possible to fully form the character of a perfect person with admonitions, speeches, lectures, but attitude and example serve to better realize the noble goal.

According to the great thinker Farobi, every perfect person is an example for others. With their wonderful qualities, sages influence the formation of the spirituality of others. An example is an important spiritual factor of social education. Such figures as Shiroq, Tomaris, Farobi, Ibn Sina, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Amir Temur have thoroughly mastered the criteria of faith, loyalty, bravery, justice and love of knowledge, left a deep mark in world history, set an example for others, and

put forward profound ideas. With this in mind, our president I. A. Karimov: "Every person should compare his life with the exemplary life of the blessed ones, and ask whether I am a worthy successor of these scholars." They have left such a great legacy, let them evaluate their work with the feeling of what will be left of me", they put forward the idea that this should be a lesson for us.

Reforms in various fields carried out in our country - understanding of human identity, mature knowledge, broad worldview - are a big factor in our becoming specialists who have progressed in all aspects.

Every person begins to think about the meaning of life from a young age, tries to find his place in society, and accordingly his life plans and aspirations appear. The happiness and well-being of every person, family, nation, and the stability of our society depend in many ways on the correctness and humaneness of the beliefs and professions that people rely on, and how well this belief matches the noble goals and vital interests of their families, children, and people.

Young people are divided into material and spiritual interests, taking into account their vital interests and the satisfaction of their needs. Spiritual interests, in turn, are divided into political, spiritual, moral and other types.

The ideology of national independence should represent the future of this society, young people and their vital interests, and in general, it should be a source of energy for our people to achieve a safe, peaceful, prosperous and prosperous life.

As the state is the main reformer, large state social programs adopted by the initiative of our President serve to further expand the scope of good works in the direction of youth policy.

Literatures:

1. Azimov, A. A., & Avliyokulov, U. M. (2019). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ ЭПОХИ АБУ АБДУЛЛАХ РУДАКИ. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 560-562.

2. Темиров, Ш. Т., & Азимов, А. А. (2016). Экономический и культурный рост народов центральной Азии в IX-X веках. In *Интеграция современных научных исследований в развитие общества* (pp. 104-105).

3. Азимов, А. А., & Темиров, Ш. Т. (2016). Политическая и социальная жизнь в бухарском эмирате во взглядах ахмада дониша. In *Интеграция современных научных исследований в развитие общества* (pp. 66-67).

4. Azimov, A. A. (2022). PHILOSOPHICAL AND ETHICAL IDEAS OF THE EARLY RENAISSANCE OF THE EAST IN CENTRAL ASIA AND THEIR REFLECTION IN THE VIEWS OF ZAKARIA AR RAZI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(7), 57-62.

5. Азимов, А. А., & Темиров, Ш. Т. (2016). КУЛЬТУРНАЯ И АРХИТЕКТУРНАЯ ВЗАИМОВЛИЯНИЯ ВОСТОКА И ВОСТОЧНОЙ ЕВРОПЫ С БУХАРОЙ. In *Современные тенденции развития науки и производства* (pp. 33-34).

6. Азимов, А. А. ўғли Рўзиев, АШ (2022, December). ОСОБЕННОСТИ КНИГИ АВЕСТА. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS* (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 37-42).

7. ВЗГЛЯДЫ РУДАКИ О ВОСПИТАНИИ ЧЕЛОВЕКА АА Азимов - Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2023 515-523

8. SCIENCE, LITERATURE AND POETRY IN TRANSOXIANA AND KHORASAN IX-X CENTURIES.

АА Abdullayevich - MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE, 2023 247-260

9. Мирзакулов, Б. Т. (2015). Дипломатические и торговые связи Бухары с Россией XVI–XVIII вв. *Молодой учёный*, 20, 548.

10. Мирзакулов, Б. Т. (1994). Рабочая кооперация Узбекистана в 20-е-начале 30-х гг.

11. Atoyev, J. H., & Saloxov, A. Q. (2022). KONSTITUTSIYADA OILA HUQUQI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(TSTU Conference 2), 637-640.

12. Salokhov, A. Q. (2023). METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF USING THE IDEAS OF BUKHARA NOVELTY IN FORMING TOLERANCE IN YOUNG PEOPLE. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(8), 171-178.

13. Салохов, А. К. К АНАЛИЗУ ИДЕЙ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ ТУРКЕСТАНСКОГО ДЖАДИДИЗМА В КОНТЕКСТЕ ЕЕ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ. *ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ОЛИЙ ВА ЎРТА МАХСУС ТАЪЛИМ ВАЗИРЛИГИ МИРЗО УЛУҒБЕК НОМИДАГИ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН МИЛЛИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТИ ФУҚАРОЛИК ЖАМИАТИ ШАКЛЛАНИШИНИ МОНИТОРИНГ*, 464.

14. Салохов, А. Қ. БУХОРО МАЪРИФАТПАРВАРЧИЛИГИНИНГ ТАРИХИЙ-ФАЛСАФИЙ ТАҲЛИЛИ.

15. Murodov, S. A. (2022). Relationship between the universe and man in the works of Fariduddin Attor. In *International conference: problems and scientific solutions* (Vol. 1, No. 6, pp. 35-41).

16. Мурадов, С. А. Современные методы философии и их значение в развитии мышления человека. *Актуальные исследования*, 51.

17. Муродов, С. А. (2009). Ибн Сино, Аттор ва Навоий асарларида кушлар тимсоли. *Имом ал-Бухорий сабоқлари», Маънавий-маърифий, илмий-адабий журнал. Тошкент*, 273-276.

18. Муродов, С. А. кизи Касимова, ФФ (2022, December). ФИЛОСОФИЯ ДИЗАЙНА: ОСОБЕННОСТИ И СУЩНОСТЬ. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS* (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 51-59).

19. Санжар, М. (2020). Взгляды Фаридуддина Аттара на бытие. *Международный журнал прикладных исследований. ИДЖАР*, 6(6), 34-36.

20. МУРАДОВ, С. А. СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ ФАРИДУДДИНА АТТОРА. *МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО "Издательство Молодой ученый", 51, 529-531.*

21. Aslonovich, M. S., & Zaynura, M. (2023, June). NATIONAL DRESSES OF CENTRAL ASIA: AS A COMPONENT OF" CULTURE OF DESIGN". In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 170-177).

22. Aslonovich, M. S., & Zaynura, M. (2023, June). NATIONAL DRESSES OF CENTRAL ASIA: AS A COMPONENT OF" CULTURE OF DESIGN". In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 170-177).

23. Мурадов, С. А. (2023, June). ФАРИДУДДИН АТТОР-ВЕЛИКИЙ ШЕЙХ ВОСТОКА. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 149-160).

24. Muradov, S. A. (2023). THE MAIN IDEAS OF THE FOUNDER OF THE GERMAN SCHOOL OF PHILOSOPHY. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(7), 588-594.

25. Sanjar, M. One of the Factors of Purity of the Heart is Futuwat. *International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology*, 98-101.

26. Sanjar, M. (2020). The views of Fariduddin Attar on being. *International journal of applied research. IJAR*, 6(6), 34-36.

27. Nurmatova N. U. THE WORK “MAQOMOTI YUSUF HAMADONIY” BY ABDULKHOLIK GHIJDUVONIY—A SAMPLE OF RESPECT TO THE MASTER” //Central Asian Problems of Modern Science and Education. – 2019. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 210-218.

28. Нурматова Н. У. ЮСУФ ҲАМАДОНИЙ ТОМОНИДАН ХОЖАГОН ТАЪЛИМОТИГА КИРИТИЛГАН БИРИНЧИ РАШҲА //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С. 565-576.

29. UMAROVNA, N. N. Four basis analysis of human perfection in the work of Yusuf Khamadani, Odobi tariqat. *International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology*, 7(4), 1-3.

30. Nurmatova N. U. Logical analysis of Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani's work "Maqomoti Yusuf Hamadoni"/ISSN (Online): 2455-3662 EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)-Peer Reviewed Journal //Volume. – Т. 7. – С. 417-420.

31. Djuraev A. et al. Cotton increase the efficiency of cleaning as a result of improving the unit for cleaning small and large wastes //AIP Conference Proceedings. – AIP Publishing, 2023. – Т. 2789. – №. 1.

32. Нурматова, Нигора, and Нодиржон Сафоев. "ШКОЛА СУФИЗМА ЮСУФА ХАМАДОНИ В БУХАРЕ." *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE*. Vol. 2. No. 15. 2023.

33. Нурматова Н. У. ЮСУФ ҲАМАДОНИЙ ТОМОНИДАН ХОЖАГОН ТАЪЛИМОТИГА КИРИТИЛГАН БИРИНЧИ РАШҲА //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С. 565-576.

34. Nurmatova, N. U. Logical analysis of Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani's work "Maqomoti Yusuf Hamadoni"/ISSN (Online): 2455-3662 EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)-Peer Reviewed Journal. *Volume, 7*, 417-420.

35. Nurmatova N. U. THE WORK "MAQOMOTI YUSUF HAMADONIY" BY ABDULKHOLIK GHIJDUVONIY—A SAMPLE OF RESPECT TO THE MASTER" //Central Asian Problems of

Modern Science and Education. – 2019. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 210-218.

36. Нурматова Н. У. Юсуф Ҳамадоний ва хожагон-нақшбандия таълимотининг "назар бар кадам" рашҳаси //Zamonaviy oliy ta'lim: muammo va yechimlar. Xalqaro ilmiy konferensiya. Navoiy. – 2022. – С. 30-31.

37. Jahongir, S. (2020). Philosophical views of Umar life. *Academicia. An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal.—India*, 10(4), 360-364.

38. Shodiev, J. J. (2020). Interpretation of moral facts in the opinions of Umar Khayyam. *International engineering journal for research & development.-India*, 5(3), 143-148.
39. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. Interpretation of the image of may in the ruba of Umar Khayyam. *Monografia pokonferencyjna science, research, development*, 33, 2020-30.
40. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайём фалсафий қарашларида инсон тақдири ва эркин ирода масаласи. *Наманган давлат университети Илмий ахборотномаси*, 2, 197-204.
41. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайёмнинг асосий асарлари ва рубойларининг тузилиши, мазмуни ва таҳлили. *Илм Сарчашмалари.-Урганч*, 10, 44-47.
42. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайём рубойларининг талқин ва тавсифи. *Наманган давлат университети Илмий ахборотномаси*, 9, 206-210.
43. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайёмнинг ижтимоий-ахлоқий қарашлари. *Фалсафа ва ҳуқуқ.-Тошкент*, 3, 107-110.
44. Shodiev, J. (2021). The problem of knowledge in the philosophical views of Umar Khayyam. *Imam al-Bukhari IBS Journal*, 2.
45. Шодиев, Ж. (2022). Илк уйғониш даврида–комил инсонни шакллантириш ватарбиялашда тасаввуф таълимотининг ўрни. *Scientific Bulletin of NamSU-Научный вестник НамГУ-NamDU ilmiy axborotnomasi–2022-yil_4-сон*, 229.
46. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. Мамлакатимизда инсон қадрини юксалтиришнинг ижтимоий-фалсафий масалалари. *Қарду хабарлари. Илмий-назарий, услубий журнал. Махсус сон (Ижтимоий фанлар)*.
47. Shodiev, J. J. (2020). INTERPRETATION AND DESCRIPTION OF UMAR KHAYYAM RUBAYA. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 2(9), 206-211.
48. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2022). AGAINST IGNORANCE-FIGHTING WITH ENLIGHTENMENT THE MAIN CRITERIA IN IMPROVING HUMAN

VALUE. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(10), 1160-1164.

49. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2022). ATTITUDE TO HUMAN DIGNITY IN THE PERIOD OF AMIR TEMUR AND TEMURIDS DYNASTY. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(5), 43-47.

50. Shodiyev, J. (2021). JAMIYATDAGI MEHNAT MUNOSABATLARI SHAROITIDA MA'NAVIY SALOHİYAT. *Журнал истории и общества*, (2)

51. SHODIEV, J. (2021). SOCIO-POLITICAL LIFE AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE IN THE PERIOD OF UMAR KHAYAM. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz)*, 1(1).

52. Shodiyev, J. (2021). O'ZBEKISTONDA IJTIMOİY-SIYOSIY KOMMUNIKATSIYA RIVOJLANISHIDA RAQAMLI TPANSFORMATSIYA SIYOSATI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(2), 409-416.

53. Shodiyev, J. J. (2020). U THE QUESTION OF HUMAN DESTINY AND FREE IN THE PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF OMAR KHAYYAM. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(2), 197-202.

54. Shodiev Jahongir Jurakulovich. Interpretation of moral facts in the opinions of Umar Khayyam. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development* 2020/4/16.

55. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2023). The role of the national idea in increase of human values. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(10), 1160-1164.

56. Shodiyev Jahongir Jo'raqulovich. Inson qadri va uning huquqlari eng oliy qadriyat: tarixiy-huquqiy meros. *Ilm sarchashmalari/ Urganch* – 3.2023. 19-21.

57. Shodiyev, J. J. (2023). THE ROLE OF SCIENTIFIC THINKING AND MENTAL DEVELOPMENT IN IMPROVING HUMAN DEVELOPMENT AND VALUE. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(9), 251-261.

58. Shodiyev, J. J. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE NATIONAL IDEA IN INCREASE OF HUMAN VALUES. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(7), 616-625.

59. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2023). PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF SAGES ON HUMAN VALUES AND GLORIFYING HIM. *THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH*, 2(16), 229-238.

60. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2023, June). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ИСТОРИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ В СОЗДАНИИ ФУНДАМЕНТА ТРЕТЬЕГО ВОЗРОЖДЕНИЯ И ЕГО ЗНАЧЕНИЕ В УКРЕПЛЕНИИ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКИХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 124-130).

61. JJ Shodiev. A STEP TOWARDS HUMAN DIGNITY. *GOLDEN BRAIN* 1 (24), 59-67.

62. Музафаровна, А.М. (2022). СЕЛЬСКОХОЗЯЙСТВЕННАЯ РЕФОРМА И ВОЗНИКАЮЩИЕ КОНФЛИКТЫ. *Международный междисциплинарный исследовательский журнал Galaxy*, 10 (5), 623-626.

63. Гаффоров, А. Х., & Алимова, М. М. (2015). Интернационализация профессионального образования как требование времени. *Молодой ученый*, (2), 506-509.

64. Алимова, М. М. (2022, December). УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ВНУТРЕННЕЙ МОТИВАЦИЕЙ РАБОТНИКОВ НА БЕЗОПАСНЫЙ ТРУД И ВЫПОЛНЕНИЕ ТРЕБОВАНИЙ ОХРАНЫ ТРУДА. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 43-50).

65. Muzafarovna, A. M., & Tangrievich, M. B. (2021). FORCED COLLECTIVIZATION OF AGRICULTURE IN ZARAFSHAN OASIS (1928-1932). *Thematics Journal of Education*, 6(November).

66. Гаффоров, А. Х., & Алимова, М. М. (2016). Перспективы использования технологии сотрудничества в процессе подготовки педагога профессионального образования. *Молодой ученый*, (12), 839-841.

67. Гаффоров, А. Х., & Алимова, М. М. (2016). Психологические основы педагогического проектирования. *Молодой ученый*, (12), 837-839.
68. Гаффоров, А. Х., & Алимова, М. М. (2015). Социально-психологические факторы формирования модели педагога в современном образовательном процессе. *Молодой ученый*, (2), 504-506.
69. Алимова, М. М. (2023). «РАСКРЕПОЩЕНИЕ» ЖЕНЩИН В ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ (1920-1930 г. г). *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(8), 535-541.
70. Алимова, М. М., & Гариев, А. (2023). ПРОТИВОДЕЙСТВИЕ КОРРУПЦИИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH*, 2(24), 261-270.
71. Бафоев Ф. М. Историческая память в мировой политике. Роль ООН и других международных организаций //Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук. – 2017. – №. 1-4. – С. 180-182.
72. Бафоев Ф. М. ПРИНЦИП НЕДЕЛИМОСТИ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ //Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук. – 2018. – №. 1-1. – С. 51-54.
73. БАФОЕВ Ф. М. О ВЗАИМОСВЯЗИ ГЛОБАЛЬНОЙ, РЕГИОНАЛЬНОЙ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПРОДОВОЛЬСТВЕННОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ //АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ Учредители: ООО" Агентство перспективных научных исследований". – №. 21. – С. 53-55.
74. БАФОЕВ Ф. М. К ВОПРОСУ КОРРЕКТИРОВКИ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ ПОНЯТИЯ «МИРОВАЯ ПОЛИТИКА» В КОНТЕКСТЕ СИНЕРГЕТИКИ //АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ. – С. 31.
75. БАФОЕВ Ф. М. К вопросу о динамике современных международных отношений //АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ Учредители: ООО" Агентство перспективных научных исследований",(20). – 2022. – С. 35-37.

76. Каримов, Б. (2011). Гармонизация взаимоотношений государства, общества и человека как основа справедливого общества. постановка вопроса. *Fuqarolik jamiyati. Гражданское общество*, 8(1), 71-73.
77. Каримов, БК (2021). Гармония разума и духа. *Американский журнал социальных наук и инноваций в образовании*, 3 (05), 230–234.
78. Каримов, Б. (2023). ПРОЦЕССЫ МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ В ДОКУМЕНТАХ ГЕНЕРАЛЬНОЙ АССАМБЛЕИ ООН (2017-2019). *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH*, 2(24), 291-301.
79. Каримов, Б.К. (2023). СУЩНОСТЬ СОЗНАНИЯ И ЕГО ГЕНЕЗ. *Инновационное развитие в образовательной деятельности*, 2 (7), 532-539.
80. Aminovna, V. G. (2021). The role of social system and political ideas in achieving human prosperity. *Thematics Journal of Education*, 6(November).
81. Бердиева, Г. А. (2023). ПРАВОВАЯ И РЕЛИГИОЗНАЯ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТЬ В СРЕДНЕЙ АЗИИ В ПЕРИОД ПЕРВОГО РЕНЕССАНСА ВОСТОКА. *МОДЕЛИ И МЕТОДЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ*, 2 (24), 271-279.
82. Бердиева, Г. А. (2023). ПРИОРИТЕТЫ МОЛОДЕЖНОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(7), 524-531.
83. Бердиева, Г. А. (2023). ЁШЛАРНИ БАҒРИКЕНГЛИК РУҲИДА ТАРБИЯЛАШДА ИЖТИМОЙ ГУМАНИТАР ФАНЛАРНИНГ ТУТГАН ЎРНИ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 5(NUU Conference 2), 232-240.
84. Аминовна, Б. Г. (2022). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ВНУТРЕННИХ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ПУТЕЙ СВЯЗИ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОАЗИАТСКИХ КОРОЛЕВСТВ В РАЗВИТИИ ТОРГОВЛИ. *Web of Scientist: Международный научный исследовательский журнал*, 3, 10-12.

85. Шукриллаев, Ю. А. (2006). Бухоро амирлигида қўшин ва ғарбий иш (1756-1920 йиллар). Тарих фанлари номзоди илмий дражасини олиш учун езилган диссертация.

86. Шукурллаев, Ю. (2022, December). СОЗДАНИЕ ВОЕННЫХ УСТАВНЫХ ГРУПП ЕВРОПЕЙСКОГО ТИПА В БУХАРСКОМ ЭМИРАТЕ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE" THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS"* (Vol. 1, No. 4, pp. 42-51).

87. Шукруллаев, Ю. А. Армия Бухарского эмирата и военное дело (1756-1920 гг.). Автореферат кандидатской диссертации по истории.-Ташкент, 2006.-26 с.; К вопросу о дипломатических сношениях между Россией и Бухарой через Оренбург в конце XVIII-начале XIX веков. *Общественные науки в Узбекистане*.-1962, 7, 55-59.

88. Shukrullayev, Y. A. The Army of Bukhara Emirate and Military Affairs (1756-1920). Synopsis of candidate dissertation in history.-Tashkent, 2006.-26 pp.; On the Issue of Diplomatic Relations between Russia and Bukhara through Orenburg at the End of the XVIII-th-the Beginning of the XIX-th Centuries. *Social Sciences in Uzbekistan*.-1962, 7, 55-59.

89. Shukrullayev, Y. A., & Bahritdinovna, S. R. (2023). GERMANIYA FEDERATIV RESPUBLIKASI IQTISODIYOTINI TIKLASH HARAKATI.“IQTISODIY MO ‘JIZA”. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(7), 577-587.

90. Shukrullayev, Y. A. (2022). FRANSIYA–O ‘ZBEKISTON ALOQALARINING TARIXIY ILDIZLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 1(3), 110-113.

91. Шукурллаев, Ю. (2023). ВОЕННЫЕ РЕФОРМЫ В БУХАРСКОМ ЭМИРАТЕ ПОД ПРОТЕКТОРАТОМ. *THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH*, 2(16), 249-260.

92. Шукурллаев, Ю. А. (2023). БУХОРО АМИРЛИГИДА ҚЎШИН ТАРКИБИГА ҚАБУЛ ҚИЛИШ ҚОИДАЛАРИ, АСКАРЛАРНИНГ ҚЎШИН

ТАРКИБИДАН ҚОЧИШИ (ДЕЗЕРТИРСВО), САБАБИ ВА ОҚИБАТЛАРИ. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(8), 513-524.

93. Shukurillayev, Y. (2023). Sherbachus and Afghan Groups in the Emirate of Bukhara. *Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal*, 2(1), 34-36.

94. Sultanova, L. (2021). The historical roots of spiritual education of youth. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 461-463.

95. Mavlonova, I., Akhmetjanov, M., Vokhidova, M., Fayziev, S., & Shokirova, S. (2022, December). Experimental studies of the dynamics of the proposed design of the presser foot with an additional conical spring. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 2373, No. 2, p. 022047). IOP Publishing.

96. Vohidova, M. (2023). SOCIAL AND ETHICAL ASPECTS OF THE EXISTENCE OF TOLERANCE IN YOUNG PEOPLE. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(6), 559-566.

97. Вахидова, М. Т., & Мирзаев, У. Т. (2022, December). ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ КУЛЬТУРЫ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ В УСЛОВИЯХ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE "THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS"* (Vol. 1, No. 4, pp. 52-62).

98. Вахидова, М. Т. (2022). ДУХОВНО-НРАВСТВЕННОЕ ВОСПИТАНИЕ МОЛОДЕЖИ УЗБЕКИСТАН В КОНТЕКСТЕ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(7), 82-90.

99. Султонова, Л. С. (2023). ИЖТИМОЙ-ГУМАНИТАР ФАНЛАРНИ ЎҚИТИШДА ПЕДАГОГИК ИННОВАЦИЯ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН ФАОЛИЯТНИНГ УЗВИЙЛИГИ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 5(NUU Conference 2), 633-639.

100. Sulstonova, L. (2023). Upbringing Mature Person. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 4(3), 71-73.

101. Султанова, Л. С. (2023). ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТЬ В ВОСПИТАНИИ ПОДРОСТОЯЩЕГО ПОКОЛЕНИЯ. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(7), 557-564.

102. Султонова, Л. С. (2022). МЕСТО ИНЖЕНЕРНОЙ ПЕДАГОГИКИ В ПОДГОТОВКЕ БУДУЩИХ ИНЖЕНЕРОВ. *YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS*, 1(6), 29-34.